

Some Concepts of Space, Time, and Lengths in Simplified Chinese*

An Analytical Linguistics Approach

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Abstract:- The article explains on the two-year experiment after the author's finalization of dissertation. The thesis of the dissertation was hidden in the last chapter with analytical linguistics. It was done so with the fascist development of the Chinese Communist regime with neo-Nazi characteristics. Since numerous prior warnings on the political downshifts & coup d'état in China was willfully ignored by the university, the linguistic innovations in dissertation found a balance between multilateralism and outer space (security). The experiments were conducted with a combination of physical unit analysis & thermonuclear dynamics analysis. It describes the experiment process in terms of gravitation as gravitational singularity and Bekenstein-Penrose singularity. Detailed research process is elaborated in the article concerning the sociopolitical interactions the research involved.

Keywords:- Thermonuclear Astrochemistry; Alternative Cosmology; Black Hole Singularities; White Hole; String Theory.

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Research Background

Cadredized education with machine training has been adopted in higher education standardization for many years. The author has been aware of P. R. China's human trafficking capabilities since 2010 without sufficient direct evidence. [1] The author has always been engaged in social inquiries on human rights and democratization, and proposed on the nationalism issues for graduate research in 2017. [34] Either with empirical findings reported or evidential reference articles, the administrative staff of the *Communication University of China* suppressed the topical issue as the

dictatorial accomplice. As per the established rules and regulations, the author completed the research with field trips in the United States of America. There is no evidence supporting the legitimacy of P. R. China's military-civil fusion strategy claims other than militant coercion on the civil society. With less discretion, I sent Several versions of the manuscripts via WeChat to my academic advisor *Ouyang Changlin*¹, reporting on the *coup d'état* before it was solidified by the constitutional change, removing term limits².

My academic advisor was temporarily removed from the university at some point for the political situations in the university and in Hu'nan province.³ Remembering the previously unevicenced knowledge in human trafficking, I adopted different strategies for the research *in leu* of any external assistance. [1] I applied for Yale School of Drama once for my social functioning and acquired some books censored by the Communist Party of China for the evaluation on the perspectives of truth, and it was from Jonathan D. Spence's *The Search for Modern China* I got the map on the epistemological histories concerning the thermonuclear knowledge of global history and Russia hegemony's dominating influence on the foundation of the P. R. China communist regime. I reported on the thermonuclear histories in my new manuscripts to refute the power politics underlying the dictatorial hypotheses, but again denied by the university's dissertational commission. It was followed by a Xinhua News piece on objecting America's deployment of nuclear weapons in outer space. [1] Based on my scientific evaluation and judgement on the piece of information, I continued with the research on outer space laws. [28]

With the deep realization on the impossibility of reasoning with the dictatorial constructs, and the knowledge on the artificial intelligence deployments in the social

¹ Although a former Chinese Communist Party member, he has a history of democratizing the Hu'nan Television from Communist propaganda political branches, and is LGBTQIA+ friendly based on the television program developments and management. It was the main reason I got into contact with him via private connections to be my academic advisor before application to the MBA program, without whom admitting students in the university I would not have applied.

² The manuscripts mainly reported on the *de facto* moves of the military with categorical imperatives. I am not against a

unification of a culturally homogenous civilization but against a unitary party structure of a fascist nation & Nazist approaches in some domestic policy practices & in international law.

³ My artist cousin's wife, somewhat like a sister-in-law to me, recommended me to apply to my academic advisor and told me the histories. But it was with some retired liberal professors in the Communication University of China I got into contact with him.

networks with individually targetable mass surveillance, in order to route the machine-readable analysis of the algorithms, linguistic innovation was conducted on the concepts of space, time, and lengths in the simplified Chinese language in the final version of the dissertation.⁴ [2] The analytical insight came from the folk Chinese language use as dissecting individual Chinese characters into horizontal and longitudinal halves. The analytical linguistic method experimented with cross-cultural communications and knowledge production faced by the global surveillance regime with intrusions on cybersecurity both in public & private sectors. It was explicated on my WeChat account and also tested the Chinese dictatorial ambitions on maritime with the Russian hegemony, with the recombination of Chinese linguistic conceptualizations.⁵ [3] The dissertation's power political perspective reading is an intended delusion and the recombined linguistic meaning can only be comprehended in general relativity, cosmology, and cosmogony. It is thus intended to manage the humanitarian risks with the artificial intelligence implemented for societal control under power politics, dictatorship, and long-broken dysfunctional social justice systems.

All the subsequent astronomical & cosmological researches benefited from the simplified linguistic concept on the "hour" (时), which can be longitudinally dissected into "sun" (日) and "inch" (寸). The dimensions on the concept of hour were thus converted to the extendable dimensions among space, time, and lengths. [4] [3] It is with this regard, the linguistic analysis also served as an analysis on the fundamental notions of physical quantities with cultural linguistic studies on the human persons of the civilization. Such conceptualization both preserved the international protocols of time, and simplified the thought process in local universe analysis with cosmic samplings and special relativity, hence Lorentz transformation. [4] The article explains on the conceptual aspects underlying the subsequent researches on an

ex post facto basis upon the conclusion of the motivation behind the research activities, namely the ecological relevance in astronomical & cosmological sciences.⁶ [5] [6]

B. Article Component

The article is written in an intersubjective manner. It puts the original conceptualization into the contextual framework of modern astronomy. The first section details on the conceptual underpinnings of the linguistic concept. For the intercultural context of the analytical linguistics, the first section is labeled methodology in the intersubjective philosophy of epistemology that counteracts the Chinese offensive dualist approaches in international law with psychological warfare in the ontological cyber domains. [1] Apart from the mental & psychological resilience gained from clowning & physical acting training initially designed for theatrical performance, the agility and creativity in the cosmological consciousness in relation to modern astronomical instrumentation was initially conceptualized and put into pragmatic research & observational cosmology, hence the experimental aspect of the observations. [3] Beneath the measures of self-preservation against gross human rights abuses, torture, and inhumane treatments by the Chinese Communist Party & its dictating government, unit analysis is the key message in the randomized literature produced as a defense mechanism in economic coercions. [2]

The second section derives the Schwarzschild radius version to the gravitational solution. It explains on the plasma imaging which borrowed energy from the quantum system, with insights on the histograms from the multiple-slit experiment. [7] The third section puts the research into context of plasma cosmology initiated by Hannes Alfvén, and resumes the inquiries of the natural sciences disregarding current political situations.⁷ [21] Such an approach in gravitation and gravitation of the white hole bridges the multiverse and (super)string theory with current hydro-sampling.⁸ The bosonic strings are explained by ejected white hole mass. [14]

⁴ During the research process, I noticed that they may be able to breach cyber security with personal devices via Apple airdrop, for example. Static DNSs with Chinese internet providers are within their normative spheres, and dynamic DNSs may be hacked by satellite informatics operations based on my experience in the 2019 trip in the U.S.A.

⁵ The new headmaster of the Communication University of China read out the superficial language that accords with the maritime ambitions of the dictator behind the Russian hegemony in two consecutive years of graduation ceremonies as per the WeChat feed of the university. This was how their own fundings had been used to convict their own crimes breaching the spirit of outer space laws. Deeply knowing their rationale on obstructing the WHO's global public health emergency decisions, when a professional in the financial sector approached me via WeChat, I gave advices in balancing the underlying humanitarian crisis on food supplies in civil societies.

⁶ Based on the good faith, I endowed one book I did not read to the charity auction event held by the MBA program. It was written by a British author on the cross-cultural linguistics on the fundamental basics of Chinese characters. This was a precaution on possible evils of recruiting child soldiers from

orphanages, as I noticed on the regime's tight controls on the NGOs.

⁷ Dialectic processes with the human traffickers with continued and on-going harassments have been conducted. Given the signs of subtle hints on my whereabouts which reflected some of my thinking processes on how could I fulfill my marriage in New York City in 2019, satellite trafficking was confirmed and possible calculations of my human behavior by artificial intelligence may have been involved. Such dialectic evidences can only be read in context and more to my own awareness, therefore, more subtle coercion & interest calculation may have been involved in the regime's gross human rights breaches. The dialectic processes have been the same with my previous interactions with people I came across in the Chinese society. Many of them were retired soldiers under dictatorial commands, and I offered my words for their repent as they confessed to me the unforgivable crimes they did as a human being.

⁸ For some whiles I wondered if the white hole on Trifid Nebula could have been the time crystal. But the more detailed analysis on the physical components & particle interactions regarding the dark and antimatter got the better of my rationality.

The fourth section explains on the leap thinking that led to the continuity of the observational experiment beyond the singularity. The observational schemes are conventional, even though the choice for observation was not. It was the aim of the whole experimental series to gather the scientific evidence on the rationale of the 1985 outer space arms control text. [28] Ironically, however, the whole experiment series proved that subtle technologies funded with malign intensions can have more profound impact on the universe and human security than the visible war crafts. [5] [35]

The article concludes that cosmic censorship hypothesis is not necessarily true but physically reasonable with instrumentation limitations on standardized protocols. It thinks that Klein cosmology has the best developmental potential for further theory-building in cosmology beyond the D-brane, and supplementary to condensed matter cosmology in instrumentation development & industrial applications. The research result may have some theoretical conflicts with M-brane theory and Big Bang cosmology. This can only be resolved by a compatible cosmological solution and is currently with the negative cosmological constant. [3] In observational cosmology, the one-time breaking of all fundamental symmetries to the new perspective will be deliberated upon. [3] There is a possibility that black holes are formed by white holes' absorption on cosmic neutrinos, and the antimatter plasmas releasing such energies via activation of galactic nuclei made the naked singularity of the white hole visible as the time crystal, explaining the direct observation on the fifth cosmic force. [4] [5] This can be the intersection of the experimental observation with M-brane. Direct testing on (super)string theory has never been conducted, for the rational concern on the systemic damage it can cause. The theoretical inputs with observational result(s) may contribute to some new perspectives the M-brane does not cover.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Linguistic Conceptualization

The concept of time is an epistemic but not ontological subject. It captures temporal motions that are not specific to gravity. The concept of time in cosmology cannot be explicated as the subjective experiential constituents, and the atomic & subatomic descriptions is limited in large scale quantity descriptions. The literal conceptual preparation simplified the scientific communication process in language, and converted the concept of hour to be applicable both to the subjective experiential space of the observer, and the observed ontological solar space. It means the vectorization of observational experience is created by the linguistic conceptualization, and can be converted to objective ontology in real-time with existing modern technologies.

When I look out of the window, I see time as the location I am in; when I am concentrated on the interface screen, I see the motion of the cosmos in its temporal nature.

⁹ If they broadcasted the dissertation with the dictatorial regime, further marginal conflicts could have arisen for the time bought for the research. Preventive measures were communicated via a Coursera course on decoupling U.S.

In the first sense, signal transmittance in the speed of light in the solar deployed instrumentation shapes the initial inner sphere of time, i.e., information with relativistic speed. In the second sense, information does not exist in the location of the observer, i.e., information is not perceived as the property of light but the epistemic object that can be explored & reorganized via qualitative procedural processing. Further quantitative methods can thus turn the structured information to ontological objects in the first sensible space, *vice versa*. [30-32] The linguistic simplification of time in an ontological light cone is the key conceptualization that assisted to merge Newtonian gravity with gravity in Einsteinian & Lorentz transformation with data practice. [4]

The perception of motion in relation to the earth's movement in the cosmos was conceptualized as the energetic phenomena dynamics instead of the solar centric notion of earth-centered time. Such astrochemical perception in the observational data is thermonuclear in nature. No specific quantitative method was devised in the conceptualization, since such a method is medium-dependent. The dissertation mainly aimed to exhibit the thermonuclear outer space environment with the black hole and white hole, so that the severity of environmental issues can be addressed to the regime & military stakeholders. It used an exclusion principle because of the norms in discourses the regime violates for too long. [5] The methodological approach in linguistics can potentially have a transborder effect in scientific communications on outer space issues, hence shaped the multilateral conceptual framework in the researches.⁹

B. Clowning & Physical Acting

In thermonuclear astrophysics & astrochemistry, the mental resilience on "spooky action at a distance", and psychological balance between the negative emotions and instrumentation rationales, were balanced by the previous clowning & physical acting trainings by *Christopher Bayes* in *Yale Center Beijing* and New York city between 2017 and 2019. The initial vision on an earth-centered (observational) cosmology was conceptualized during one section, as the observer walks on earth in clockwise & counterclockwise motions in relation to the solar-centric motions of the earth. The positive discovery modes and deep explorations on the sources & shifts in emotions contributed to the agilities in experimental & research activities with the data practice, including using the nearby star as a macroparticle source to the multiple-slit traces in black hole & white hole. [4] [7] The clown trainings helped with reducing the traumatic responses from the human trafficking harms, and transforming the negative energy of the human body to positive energies of the human body for positive knowledge production. [5] However, the trauma of being silenced with psychological attacks & threats from being tortured with inhumane treatments were deeper, and is being healed by reading on dark psychology for self-diagnosis from Machiavellian harms.¹⁰ [1] [8]

dollars with RMB in deescalating the global financial intrusions of the regime's cyber practice.

¹⁰ Deeper theological explorations have been ongoing between the Vatican's stance on procreation and queer theology; the postulates of original sins and bioethics.

The techniques picked up from clowning & physical acting helped to resolve the dual aspects of consciousness between data and physical locality, and between relativistic realities and solar-centric realities on earth. The vectorization of the Hamiltonian in relation to the cosmological constant in the experimental research series effectively balanced between the instrumentation space with information feedback, and information space of the observer with thermonuclear astrochemical & astrophysical consciousness. [3] [4] [5] Dimensional fear from the observed fifth cosmic force on the Trifid Nebula surged during the data analysis, and worsened the traumatic responses from the inhuman treatments by the P. R. China Ministry of Education affiliated university & companies.¹¹ [3] [5] [9] Even though some of them, including some of my high school teachers and high school classmates in the PLA affiliated university may knew about the situation I was in with the inhumane treatments, they chose to follow orders and remained silent, except on giving me subtle hints for aversive behaviors that negatively impact on my marriage & reunion with my husband. Therefore, the social theater approach in sustaining the continuity of the research had some negative influence on aversive behaviors as well.¹² [1]

For the consciousness on the ontological extrapolation Chinese cyber with artificial intelligence empowered semantics & psychological data coding methods that is highly intrusive on individual privacies, the analytical linguistics approach was the foundation for the consecutive paralleling astronomical & cosmological researches. [1] It could have temporarily counteracted some of the illicit programs, and reserved some fundamental notions of reality for the healing process with scientific consciousness and cognitive psychology.¹³ It is with this regard, the dissertational piece with analytical linguistics was a risk management mechanism on the mass human rights breaches conducted by the Chinese Communist Party of the P. R. China governmental & state apparatus.¹⁴ [2] Since P. R. China uses a nationalism principle

in “legislation” in the unitary party “constitution” with double-measure coercion, Physical acting & clowning techniques in communications were also used for the “oscillation” between P. R. China “reality” and humanitarian-principle based legal entities.¹⁵ [10] [11]

C. Unit Analysis — The Issues of Time and Length

The conversion between time and lengths in astrophysics is more quantifiable than astrochemistry, even with quantum physics assistances. The computability of the cosmological method was corroborated by the initial publication’s peer-reviews, but the astrochemical method with Lorentz transformation approach remains unsolved for now.¹⁶ [12] [13] With the conservation of momentum¹⁷, Newton’s first law combined with Einstein’s equation gives the first principle of astrophysical motions in terms of thermonuclear astrochemistry, hence length & time conversions between astrophysics & astrochemistry in special relativity. The one-body solution in the deductive truth is hence:

$$\frac{F}{m} = \frac{\Delta m a c^2}{\Delta E} \quad (1)$$

This is a partial expression on the other cosmic forces’ observational signature on gravity of the observed body. With the equivalence of centripetal force & centrifugal force in different directions, the angular momentum of the thermonuclear force in a two-body problem can be simplified as:

$$\frac{m_1}{m_2} r_1 r_2 = \frac{v^2}{\omega^2} \quad (2)$$

The dimensional spins of v cannot be resolved with the earth-centered gravitational constant G , and Einstein temporally resolved it with $g_{\mu\nu}$ in the field approach, I initiated the linguistic approach “天圆地方”¹⁸ conceptualizing

¹¹ The observational result was expected & anticipated before the observation, but the actual confirmation on the observational result triggered the victim psychology against the perpetrator, yet I always adopted the approaches of persuasion, nonviolence, forgiveness, knowledge production and etc. dealing with these issues. The moral psychology against retribution made me think the only moral & rational choice was to commit suicide and keep the knowledge as a secret.

¹² However, without the social theater approaches, I would not have collected enough evidence on the perpetrators and formed the evidence chain for procedural justice.

¹³ The original theory is my sense of reality in time, with special relativity as the anchor and general relativity as the sense of societal reality.

¹⁴ The risk lies with its maritime military ambitions with global market access by centralized banking and dualism approaches in international law. The latter is also the source of gross human rights breaches. In my previous research in outer space laws, I also noticed that the state department of the U.S.A. adopted preliminary precautions measures by limiting exports of outer space related technologies. However, according to my research findings, *ex post facto*, the omission with LASER technologies & energy potentials

still did not prevent the happenings of mass photon releases by the Mozi quantum satellite.

¹⁵ With the feedback that the quantum number of a neutron star is 500, the severity of the issues was mentally weighed.

¹⁶ This is because of the unconventional protocol I used obtaining the key evidence on white hole. Think of it as a Prometheus operation.

¹⁷ Herein I have not referred to angular momentum, since it involves deeper questions on gravitational collapse in Penrose’s paper in the 1970s, with instrumentation gravity involved in the concerns. But the subtle (a)symmetries between the event horizon and inner ergoregion structures with gauge fields, combined with the dimension of histograms, corroborate with the linear quadruple electroweak force’s unification with the strong force.

¹⁸ Roughly, “sky circle and ground square”, or “sky globe and ground cubic”. The Chinese civilization never conceptualized the notion of negative infinity with Taoism as the primitive notion of calculus in Chinese civilization philosophy. It is therefore, the anti-enlightenment revisionist approaches in education the CPC adopts in propaganda & indoctrination that shaped the expansionism tendencies of the regime. The reintroduction of the four dimensional space

the dilemmas on the issues about describing gravity as a fraction of time in relation to mass(es). This approach is no different with light cones. Since the lengths are geometrical in *Equation (2)*, replacing v^2 with c^2 , dimensional momenta can be inducted with Einstein's equation and *Equation (1)*. The linearity and angular shifts with antimatter presence & quadruple momentum were described in the article first published in the series. [4]

For Lorentz transformation, finding the arrow of time was trickier reassembling the astrochemical information based on nuclear physics & chemistry. The instrumentation space predetermined the gravitational fields in the solar space, and the destructive perturbation can cause many blind spots with observation. Partial independence from general relativity was thus achieved. This was also the reason that the observational experiment with ground-based observatories was conducted supplementary to the data experiment. [3] A simple ideation of gravity in relation to Lorentz transformation as thermonuclear astrochemistry is reverting the terms of gravitational constant to the physical unit of $\frac{s^2 kg}{m^3}$. However, this creates a dimensional problem with the ground states, even though it yielded anticipated results. The fractional measures, aided by astrochemical induction with the $s^2 kilogram$ terms and conformable to instrumentation safety, has another weakness — the accumulation of mass as the dimension goes up. String theory as an anti-entropic theory, albeit cannot be experimentally confirmed for instrumentation safety concerns, solved the dilemma with atomic & subatomic particle physics. [36] Even though string theory is frozen in the conformal boundaries due to antimatter electromagnetism, by historical analysis, the Schwarzschild radius that predicted & defined the existence of black holes is exactly the one-body problem version of *Equation 2*, which means the unit of mass is irrelevant in regard of motion.¹⁹ Thereby, with current states of physics, the advancement of the astronomical sciences can't progress without the advancement of cosmology, underlying the fifth force empirically discovered in the experiments. [5]

The integral aspects of all four types of black hole solutions are dependent on the gravitational constant, hence the inevitability of singularity. [14] As guided by the decay momentum, the anti-entropic approaches cannot keep up with the asymmetric oscillation forces on a cosmic scale with the negative cosmological constant.²⁰ [5] [4] It means that every inch a celestial object moves, an astrochemical quantity $\Delta\rho$ changes in relativistic velocities in forms of plasmas. [4] In an idealized state without accounting for intergalactic forces & bias factors, the one-body force in the juxtapose is hence: [12]

$$F_1 = m_1 \Delta\rho ac^2 \quad (3)$$

of earth in intercultural communication was the key philosophy.

¹⁹ I only mean that the unit is irrelevant but the quantity is not irrelevant.

²⁰ With the influence of physical signals, especially the impacts of high energy photon signals, the fundamental

With reference to *Equation (1)*, the change of light information in the instrumentation energy as in $\Delta\rho$, is the energy exchange in particular angular momenta with the instrumentation in relative motion. The force carried in particular cosmic arrays are never negative but can be in consecutive momenta. As with the possibly machine-readable sentences that mirrored the maritime ambitions of the fascism inflictions to the civil society even before the constitution change²¹, the halves of the characters in the sentences reflected the solar system in *Equation (3)*. The dimensions of time in *Equation (3)* thus becomes astrochemical in relation to energy and cosmic force, and the force / astrochemical ratio was then reflected in the quantum realm as resonance imaging technique. [3] Linear backward induction with astrophysics is possible, but oscillation in the non-repeatable vastness of universe in the corner of the solar system makes it exceedingly complex. This also asserts that without the cosmic force in length, gravitational radiation makes no concrete meaning in space, which may underlie Einstein's later hesitancy in his works. The linearity of the equation is the form of spatial induction:

$$\frac{\rho a}{F_1} = \frac{1}{m_1 c^2} \quad (4)$$

Depending on the orientation and physical, chemical, & information system, the dimensional extensions with number theory can be expressed with my theorem on the value of $0 \approx \frac{1}{i^{4n}}, n \rightarrow \infty$. [3] This is a mechanically valid expression but not necessarily reflects local universe realities. [15] The advantage of this method is that it can be incorporated into binaries and possible future quantum computers with alterations in π and ascension(s) in e , yet the force generated by light cones in angular momenta lack one crucial dimension in gravity. It is with this question, by the empirical discovery from the black hole & white hole juxtapose, the article discusses on the possibility of gravity that is particle-physics independent. [12]

III. THE PLASMA IMAGING RESULTS IN SCHWARZSCHILD RADIUS

A convenient way to put the dimension of gravity into the germinal astrochemistry is to put the Schwarzschild radius into *Equation (2)*:

$$\frac{4G^2 m_1^2}{c^4} = \frac{v^2}{\omega^2} \quad (5)$$

It can be seen as the reduced dimension of relativistic gravity that was experimentally depended upon with the earth-based MicroObservatory with ΔE_2 . [3] It means that, under the gravity of the linearized unseen of black hole & white hole in

symmetries are bound for large-scale changes in the human senses of time as future & present.

²¹ Since I combined theology in the dissertation document with previous antithesis writings refuting the intention of the Three Gorges Dam construction, I used the sentence analogically on hydrodynamics.

the earth's field²², the equators are naturally conceptualized as the dynamic dipole momentum. [4] [12] White hole induction was thus made possible with:²³ [3]

$$\frac{4G^2 m_1^2 \Delta m_2^2}{\Delta E_2^2} = \frac{v^2}{\omega^2} \quad (6)$$

It means that with enough acceleration momentum, white holes can actually be observed proportional to the contraction of gravitational curve on angular momentum. This runs with some subtle differences to the relativistic gravity of Einstein's work, with the elements of Archimedes' lever in the three-body problem. [16] Even though the observation & data system was more like a Minkowski space, the start of the observation with the Magellanic Cloud with the strong force slit and weak force resonance in time dilation satisfied the inertial condition.²⁴ [3] [17] However, for detailed observation on the local universe juxtapose in thermonuclear astrochemical binding, both atomic and light clocks need to be used, with the difficulty of the distance coverage with local spin(s) relative to the vantage point(s) of observation, with the antimatter electromagnetism included. It is also with this regard, the G^2 constant can be seen as the velocity in ground (earth) based instrumentations. [4]

A conceptual Möbius strip of the earth in the solar system in relation to the local juxtapose was thus created, in the direction of the Minkowski space that was confirmed to be computable by the reviewer's feedback. [12] Due to the limitation of the experiment environment with the aid of internet,²⁵ only the white hole part was observed relative to the black hole, instead of the other way around in current observational protocols²⁶, with the cosmic forces as arrow of time in relation to the lengths covered by the observations. It is a pity that gravitation was not put into the interest of the

observation series for the evidence gathering. [3] The motivation of the observations was more incentivized to gather the empirical data on the clear and present danger that the Communist Party of China has done with the realpolitik approaches on the scientific communities.²⁷ [5] [9]

As with the indication of the plasma imaging with quadruple electroweak momentum in **Figure 1**, apart from the exotic metal-insulator place-holder on the ring singularity beside the white hole plasma, two neutron highlights on the black hole side and one on the white hole side were observed on the details. This also underlies the reason that one reviewer's confirmation on supermassive neutron stars increased the confidence of the white hole observations. [3] In the relativistic gravitational fields, the James-Webb Alignment Evaluation Image's further details on the perturbation, possibly from the active galactic nuclei portal, judged from the reference on the disproportional distribution of miniature black holes and neutron stars (as ejected white hole material), represents *Equation 6* in space-based instrumentation. [18] This represents a four-dimension time in the elevation of space-based technologies. The empiricism in pragmatic space-based technologies can be adjusted with instrumentation parameters to the gravitational constant, hence the contingency of the methodology.²⁸ In a physical cosmology sense, this observer-centered privilege access, with the observer in time included in the Möbius strip abstraction of the discrete approach to the pre-Big-Bang Conformal Cyclic Cosmology, increased the efficacy of the experimental approaches. [15] [16] The conservation of (possibly angular included) momentum in the idealized two-body solution in gravity & cosmic force(s) rested on the presumption of $\Delta\rho$ being considered as an equal total amount. The time in motion of the instrumentation space does not trespass current

²² The earth is seen as in the "cosmic gravitational background".

²³ It is the progression of time to the counterclockwise motion of the earth.

²⁴ The concept was also used in the 2021 NASA Data Challenge but may be less understood on the rationale and was not explained previously. There looks to be some similarities of concept with the design of the Event Horizon Telescope, with possible differences in the premise of anchoring. The intersection may be with general relativity in its variation. The experiment observation's premise of white hole was on the Kerr-Newman type on NGC 3034, which is less complicated to prove with limited observations and by the histogram(s) with the oscillated black hole & white hole parts.

²⁵ Even though my internet is in the Great Firewall under surveillance, and received continued constant harassment from the dictatorial regime's cyber police forces, it is nonetheless still internet. Only that how they use information for illicit purposes or related interests & gains was not my focus in the calculations.

²⁶ The white hole observation results thus accord with the Pauli exclusion principle.

²⁷ Further communications were made with the International Court of Justice and United Nations Human Rights council based on the crimes against humanity and justice for the diverse gender population with different sexual orientation in

founding a family. The current widespread coercion is making it a fascist country & nation. Self-orientated psychodynamics healing process has been conducted with some online communities in the sciences. This also underlies some necessary sexism with the Freudian psychology in defying the structural stigma with necessary self-preservation. Some subtle sexism gender hints were used on the communication of international security in multilateralism with the presence of psychological cyber warfare initiated by the CPC, which was also one reason why the research took 5 years with immigration procedures. The sexism took the knowledge background from the European art communities' artistic & academic approaches defying the structural stigma in gender biases, and the moral writings I learned on American political science, with the combination to (queer) theology.

²⁸ This somewhat and somehow shapes an alternative if not replacement to general relativity. The efficacy of general relativity in space-based technologies can thence be transformed into the information sphere in the solar system. The initial conceptualization PPT was proposed to the 2022 The Science of Consciousness conference held by the University of Arizona but interrupted by the Chinese Communist Party's informatics from the PLA during the virtual format of the conference. I intended to attend in person but the VISA process might have been obstructed by the Chinese government and not the American government's refusal.

protocols of time. However, this leaves the question on the formation of black hole and the formation of white hole unanswered with the empirical anti-entropic approach.

Fig. 1 Quadruple Plasma Imaging on the NGC 3034 Kerr-Newman Type Juxtapose

Fig. 2 Ionizing radiation during the activation of galactic nuclei on NGC 3034. Courtesy@ALLWISE JPL/CalTech

IV. THE NEGATIVE ENERGY DILEMMA

Fig. 3 Actinic radiation during the activation of galactic nuclei on NGC 3034. Courtesy@ALLWISE JPL/CalTech

The negative energy dilemma with the thermodynamic laws is at the core thesis of Penrose’s philosophical assertion on the causality of space-time singularity and the Big Bang theory. [14] [15] The negative energy dilemma is also an epistemic question on whether the reconciliation between & amongst subjectivity & objectivity, and physics & metaphysical cosmology is possible. Albeit the experimental process was similar to Einstein’s aether theory approach, the differences to the Hilbert space and the breaking of Lorentz symmetry to the Big Bang theory is differentiated.²⁹ [20] The particle filtering process on M87 observation was a test on the relativistic gravitation from the both space and time like singularity. [3] Thereon, as suggested by *Equation (6)* and the data analysis that led to the imaging in *Fig.1*, plasma cosmology takes the predominance.³⁰ [21] As was with the parallel experiment process, the series of research did not put plasma cosmology into the Big Bang theory context, and only used the sun and moon observations to get a grip of earthly reality. [22] As per the data query on the IRAC system with ALLWISE for the reference on observational momenta on NGC 3034, two distinct phases of radiative process were observed during the activation of galactic nuclei exemplified by the bad pixels, namely the ionizing radiation and actinic radiation.

²⁹ I owe much gratitude to Roger Penrose’s constant care & support to young scientists in the scientific meetings that I was not able to attend in person. Even in remote settings, the strengths and grace were constantly felt. It is a pity though that I was not able to go beyond too far away from the cushions of the CCC for realistic circumstances.

³⁰ There is a subtle correlation between plasma cosmology and string theory, as exemplified by the 2021 NASA Data Challenge on M87. The results are not yet published but some manuscripts on cosmology have formed.

The evidence suggests internal radiative (thermal implied) transfer took place within the juxtapose and by causal inference led to the activation of galactic nuclei. [4] This implies that the global distribution of historic approaches reconstructing time to earlier phases of the Big Bang cosmology is not consistent with the local universe realities in space-time continuity.³¹ [21] Henceforth, I propose and assert that the appearance of negative energy is in essence indicators of plasmatic radiative thermal transfer between a black hole and a white hole. [15] By the contrast between **Figure 1** and **Figure 3**, the Big Bang singularity posture on antimatter distribution in the universe is largely under-evaluated due to the limitations on visions with current imaging and isotopic plates, thus the formation of the boundary layer. [21] Furthermore, with the exotic metal-insulator's quadruple electromagnetic locking effects on the weak force in prior observations, the subtle differences may have been largely rendered unconscious. However, the critical ionization velocity may further explain the detailed physics on the formation of the structural locking element. [23] With the resonance effect preserved in the expressions, the ΔE_2 term can be replaced by the ΔE_g term without the presumption of

cosmological causal formation of black & white holes nor the mass transfer between the two bodies via plasmas. [22]

$$\frac{4G^2 r_f^2 \Delta m_2^2}{k^2 m_2^2} = \frac{v^2}{\omega^2} \quad (7)$$

Since the equations did not put W asymmetry into account but only the electroweak flux, **Equation (7)** remains on the relativistic gravitational mass of the white hole to the black hole, which effectively describes the Trifid Nebula result. [3] [5] The [de]homeomorphism of the topological invariant Hawking points is consistent with the gravitational analysis in **Equation (7)** and the white hole observation provided the empirical proof and data. [5] [3] The resonance effect in radiative process in **Figure 4** also proves the environmental consequences faced by the photon excitations of black and white holes. [5] Even though most Hawking points are seen in the form of leptons with rippling quarks pushed by the former, there is only one Hawking point with persistent photon sphere - possibly with a combination of quarks & Higgs boson.³² In such chemical decay reference frames, the linearization of non-linear bijection into global

Fig. 4 The invariant Hawking points on NGC 3034 with topological homeomorphism.

³¹ I used the theatrical concept of classical unities in my Chinese literature to distinct the wavelength-band implications in local universes.

³² This implies that the concentration of Higgs Boson in the Hawking point may be the cause for the other fundamental

particles' movement with the black body radiation process, which means that the strong force may be caused by the unique Hawking point. This is consistent with the Small Magellanic Cloud observation during the time dilation.

distribution or conformal boundaries still fall into the possible alternatives of the Big Bang structure. [24] [25] The boson lock in the fermionic condensate with the unique Hawking point implies that r_i is relatively constant, therefore, the conformal boundary for the white hole with the trapped surface in T^2 . [14] For the M-brane developments in superstring theory, only when the chemical plasmas' influence is accounted for in the consideration of pressures, can the gravitational dimensions make concrete physical meaning. The fundamental limitations (super)string theory face is still with antimatter & antimatter electromagnetism, as is with the Big Bang theory.

V. BALLISTIC REGRESSION WITHOUT SINGULARITY

The 2021 NASA & MicroObservatory Data Challenge went in parallel with the Trifid Nebula observation. [3] **Figure 5** shows the string theory version of the thermal flows with the

energy arrow conversely correlated to the thermal arrow of time.³³ The shifts of wave-functions in inverse problems were thus conceptualized as a ballistic regression model from relativistic universe.³⁴ The Higgs mechanism in *Fig. 5* with adjusted thermal arrow of time was the methodological reference to the Trifid Nebula data analysis. [26] [3] The thermal arrow of time was the trace signature to the fifth cosmic force between the black hole and white hole. [27] With reference to the strong force and its implications for particle physics, I adhere to the order of magnitude and call it the SS force (stronger than strong force force). The methodological intuition emanated from the designs of antiballistic missiles and was inspired by the 1985 outer space arms control texts. [28] The designs of anti-ballistic missiles are a typical break on the second law of thermodynamics. The masses of such missiles are triggered by the heat inflow to the direction of the missiles.³⁵ This leap thinking from thought guided the choice of the Trifid Nebula observation, since most of the reviewers

Fig. 5 Cosmic strings on M87 with adjusted thermal arrow of time

³³ A version not adjusted for the thermal arrow was also processed.

³⁴ It is only conceptualized as such for the convenience of natural decay patterns signified by intercontinental missiles in the global concept of time in retrogression analysis.

³⁵ When I first read on Wulf's texts during my graduate research, I immediately knew America long had known the stakes in outer space with white hole and black hole. My original dissertational research purpose was to persuade the

Communist Party of China out of the ambitions in chemical weapons. My subconscious suspicion arose from the national propagandas of tree planting as a discourse on global warming. It has long transferred the costs of the Paris Agreement to the civil economy. The construction of the Three Gorges Dam, after the 1989 Tian'anmen Square Massacre and disregarding warnings from geologists, was the concrete militant move by the CPC with large-scale forced migrations.

rejected the cosmological manuscript for discretion on physics, and the implication for more exotic matter.

Essentially, the Trifid Nebula observation broke the Möbius strip and jumped to the white hole part of the juxtapose by the thermal arrow of time. The trace signature of the exotic metal-insulator was the identification for the type of the observation. The observation process implies that in relativistic universe, Möbius strips have the potential to link and jump between metaverses. This was the type theory that supported the experiment with FITS protocols. [29-32] The observational result violated the strong cosmic censorship but weak cosmic censorship remained. [33] Here I argue that singularities do not necessarily arise out of the natural universe rather than an instrumentation inevitability, which means cosmic censorship hypothesis is dependent on observers' subjective angles. [14] [3]

Since all current observational instrumentation are dependent on electromagnetic waves, the Möbius strip shifts on clockwise and counter-clockwise terms change the direction of oscillation and time arrows simultaneously. The advantage of Möbius strip conceptualizations is that time in $i^n\pi$ with earth-based instrumentation does not necessarily need to follow the existing protocols of time of earth. This gave the advantage of nuclear astrophysics & astrochemistry analyses. The data oscillation started from the weak force to the strong force, on a counterclockwise basis. It revealed the white hole crystal with relative shifts to the black hole horizon. The source for such shifts is identified by the SS force. [5] It is in this regard; the observational result violated the weak cosmic censorship as well. [33] This piece of observation trespassed the limit of Lorentz manifold and no further inductions could have been made without an antimatter-made detection plate.³⁶ With the singularity as the resting reference point in the cosmic voyages, the replacement on the trapped surface of T^2 is hence temporarily made a solution by a presumption of double-entropic singularity: [3]

$$S^2 = \left(\frac{\omega r_i \Delta m_2 \pi c^6}{h v m_2}\right)^2 \quad (8)$$

This is an empirical determinant on the SS force based on the symmetric assumption of black hole & white hole singularities. The gravitation and pressure free solution to the polyhedron circumsphere(s) in Equation (8) means that with current hydrogen sampling isotopes, hydrogen electrolysis on Schwarzschild singularity is the prototype for all black hole & white hole juxtaposes. [12] It is analogous that the ring singularity of the juxtaposes' decay momenta are the highly amplified particle colliders. [5] Further advancements in

gravitation need to be deduced from the advancement in cosmology. The modeling of such cosmology will need further quantitative data after the settlements of the author's personal affairs in transnational justice if a monist international legal order founded on universal human rights cannot be achieved temporarily.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Black hole singularity is not a singularity in time nor space. It is a singularity of thermonuclear collision velocity. [4] Such velocity is the empirical determinant to gravitation based on Klein cosmology. [21] The strengths of cosmic forces in relation to Klein cosmology are the key orders of magnitude to the thermal arrow of time to white hole observations, and the halt on decays by cosmic censorship. Hydrogen sampling from the Schwarzschild solutions in relation to Kerr-Newman juxtapose are the prototypes of the thermonuclear dynamism of the juxtaposes together with Kerr & Reissner-Nordström types. Gravitational theories can hence be derived against entropy & decay in global distributions. The ballistic regression observation may have further implications to distributions & topology, and the computability in relation to change in FITS protocols was proposed to the 2022 The Science of Consciousness conference.³⁷ The thermal arrow of time provided the initial evidence needed for the scientific developments and the breach of outer space security. [5] The current approach adopted to singularities is gravitation and pressure free in relativistic terms for oscillation. The approach changed the particle physics dependent paradigm of the (super)string theory to a black hole dependent paradigm on white hole studies. They rest on different philosophical bases between rationalism & empiricism. The observations & research activities took some risks for the imminent human-caused dangers in outer space that I noticed but did not get to prevent. [5] Future research activities will be more discrete than the current approaches out of emergencies.³⁸

From the histories on the Romanization of the Chinese language, the Vatican's fundamentalism influence in the drafting of the Chinese version of the Human Rights charter in relation to ecclesial Latin is eminent to the inequalities of the LGBTQIA⁺ population in mainland China, if not the willful misrepresentation of the fundamental spirits therein by the United Front of China that militarizes all sectors & culture including the faith of Christianity. [34] It is not to be ignored but possibly willfully neglected by the original Biblical writers that the original sin of the God by Abel and descended from Cain, was never explicitly revealed in the Old Testament. It is the theological basis on the sins of patriarchy and origin of stigmatization on LGBTQIA⁺ Christians.³⁹ In the New

³⁶ I actually submitted a PhD application proposal before the observation on such a design to University of Washington, but was later reminded on the impossible costs of such a design model.

³⁷ Such conceptualization may be premature, and if it needs to be made workable, further empirical researches will need to be conducted by experiences with the systems & more detailed rational analysis.

³⁸ In some heated discussions online, I was reminded a key detail in my thinking. Lorentz transformation based on special

relativity was based on the conversion of spatial curvature (qualitatively in linearized special relativity and quantitatively in general relativity) to local (universe's) curvature of time.

³⁹ The biblical lines in the Old Testament have many omissions that may be possibly associated with the original sins of men, women, and God. Such complexities, apart from the diversity of gender & sexual orientation, often make me wonder on the human spirits' capacities for violence, and the constant failed attempts in forming any universal ethical or

Testament, no laws of discriminatory nature were announced by Jesus Christ. [34] It has always been those who claim authority via the God in the Old Testament and through Jesus Christ in the New Testament that trespassed the liberties of humanity regardless of gender or sexual orientation. The heteronormative gender lens of heterogamy by the Vatican is the source of subjective bias on the militant intensions of the Communist blocks.

From the prior research-related activities, including the interference patterns from the dictatorial institutions both with online media communication technologies and in-person harassment settings that obstructed my VISA process, the human trafficking extrapolation has most probably been violating my intellectual property rights by utilizing my scientific outputs with financial & economic backend manipulations.⁴⁰ [1] [5] Such use of Dang'an documents combined with practical use for training CPC loyal personnel by National Scholarship Fund is the main method for technological transfers of P. R. China, and is associated with the broadcasting codes.⁴¹ The schemes of the Chinese education system have been predominantly on military import & export. Utility reading & adaptation of intellectual properties may not be a single-case issue, but the conformity of the original theory to the natural science may have been used as access to the scientific communities, and in turn, with domestic controls they find new opportunities to get market access. The sound alteration & distortion via broadcast channel was also noticed in the 2022 The Science of Consciousness during Roger Penrose's presentation after the interruption of his Plenary section. Such continuous acts constitute mental torture, with inhuman and degrading treatment considering the contents of the broadcasts with privacy intrusions and distortion on audio information even after the serious abuses on my human rights. Deeper issues on disinformation and intelligence in the international & global realm was noticed prior to these obstructions during the dissertation research. The human trafficking may have used similar techniques as digital humanity, only that it does not follow the proper ethics & morality of such disciplines, hence the criminological trace of the gross human rights abuses. [37]

Personally, the ill-adaptation of my original manuscript in the CPC Dang'an document may have been used in the global scientific communities for their technological hunt purposes. [5] It violated my intellectual property rights with deep influences on the scientific communities. From the intellectual interactions with Sir Roger Penrose online in the occasions, some influences may have been previously asserted to him, but his better judgements defended against the potential harms. However, the fundamentalism with the Old Testament still poses the issues of inequalities in the broadcastings of gender identities in the religious & secular settings of the Western World's international & global

moral values. Such as the moral values of procreation is not inherent in LGTQIA⁺ sex, yet the ethical values of raising kids does not necessarily need to involve the procreation of the married couple(s). Neither is the primitive nature of procreation prerequisite to enlightenment.

⁴⁰ The in-person harassment and following started even before the COVID-19 epidemic, including in the U.S.A. in New York

politics. [37] By the closing remarks of the conclusions, the heuristics I started since high school and put into practice with the dissertation is completed. [2] [7] [38]

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

AllWISE makes use of data from WISE, which is a joint project of the University of California, Los Angeles, and the Jet Propulsion Laboratory/California Institute of Technology;

This research is based on observations made with the NASA/ESA Hubble Space Telescope obtained from the Space Telescope Science Institute, which is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under NASA contract NAS 5-26555;

This research is based on observations made with the Galaxy Evolution Explorer (GALEX) satellite, a NASA mission led by the California Institute of Technology, obtained from the Space Telescope Science Institute, which is operated by the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy, Inc., under NASA contract NAS 5-26555;

The scientific results reported in this article are based [in part] on observations made by the Chandra X-ray Observatory;

This work is based [in part] on observations made with the Spitzer Space Telescope, which was operated by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology under a contract with NASA.

The observations are made on Harvard-Smithsonian MicroObservatory and observation data are available on Harvard Dataverse: <https://doi.org/10.7910/DVN/OBXLGX>. All data are processed by JS9-4L online and SAOImage DS9 MacOS.

I owe my gratitude to the humanitarian interventions offered anomalously online in some communications.

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City in 2019. When I was applying for a new passport for travel in 2020, I was followed by interrogative person in Chongqing too.

⁴¹ Such schema was also reflected in my undergraduate transgender-themed graduation co-production *The Lithosporic* in the voiceover track.

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